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Lessons Learned from PETRA-1: Psychological, Environmental, and Technological Research Analog

Sahba El-Shawa^{a*}, Zaina Abu-Shaar^a

^a Jordan Space Research Initiative, Amman, Jordan jsri2space@gmail.com

* Corresponding Author

Abstract

This paper presents an in-depth case study of the Jordan Space Research Initiative's PETRA-1 Mission, the first space analog mission to be held in Jordan. This all-female mission hosted a crew of 3 analog astronauts for 4 days in the Wadi Rum desert, often described as Mars on Earth. This paper details the mission's operational aspects, including habitat setup, dietary planning, communications, partnerships, and mission objectives. A significant focus of the study is on the interdisciplinary elements of the mission. PETRA-1, or the Psychological, Environmental, and Technological Research Analog, explores various areas of research necessary for future space habitation. This encompasses the social dynamics of the crew, the integration of technology such as Virtual Reality for psychological and environmental research, as well as the simulation of extra-vehicular activities (EVAs) and emergency protocols. This paper will also discuss the mission control strategy, and other operational processes put in place to ensure the simulation mimics space conditions, such as time delays and strict daily schedules. The PETRA-1 Mission aims to serve as proof of concept and a model for future permanent habitat simulations in Jordan, offering valuable insights into the design, operation, and research potential of these analog space missions. Therefore, this paper will present the lessons learned from this endeavor, emphasizing the need for interdisciplinary approaches and innovative solutions in preparing for future crewed missions to extraterrestrial environments.

Keywords: Jordan, JSRI, analog missions, space simulation, psychology, environment

Acronyms/Abbreviations

EVA	Extravehicular Activity
JSRI	Jordan Space Research Initiative
PETRA-1	Psychological, Environmental, and Technological Research Analog
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
VR	Virtual Reality

1. Introduction

The establishment of the Jordan Space Research Initiative (JSRI) in 2020 aimed to enhance space research and development in Jordan [1]. JSRI's main goal is to promote space exploration in accordance with the Jordan's national priorities as they relate to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [2]. JSRI seeks to demonstrate the concrete advantages that space technology and research can offer Earth, including technological progress and environmental sustainability. It aims to do this through two main areas: 1) Analog Missions and Space R&D, and 2) Community and Stakeholder Engagement.

The Psychological, Environmental, and Technological Research Analog (PETRA-1) Mission—the first Jordanian analog mission—represents a major achievement for Jordan as it enters the field of space research and aims to establish a prominent presence in the industry. The mission acts as a demonstration for potential analog missions in the future, providing understanding of the difficulties of space exploration

and Jordan's preparedness for similar projects. PETRA-1 highlighted JSRI's ability to carry out interdisciplinary research focusing on key elements of space missions, like human health, environmental sustainability, and technological preparedness.

Fig.1. PETRA-1 Mission Patch

The selection of Wadi Rum as the setting for PETRA-1 was based on its similarity to the Martian terrain and extraterrestrial landscape, leading it to be locally dubbed

"Valley of the Moon" [3]. Its red sand, tall rock formations, and extensive, remote landscape make it an ideal place for recreating conditions similar to Mars. The geological characteristics of the desert offer a practical setting for examining technologies, equipment, and human behaviors in harsh conditions. This contributed to selecting Wadi Rum into the best possible location for PETRA-1 to be held [4], allowing for thorough exploration of both the environmental and psychological factors of space exploration.

Fig. 2. Wadi Rum rocky terrain

2. Mission Overview

The PETRA-1 mission marked a groundbreaking step in advancing Jordan's capabilities in space exploration. As the country's first space analog mission, PETRA-1 set out to achieve a series of objectives aimed at testing interdisciplinary research approaches and simulating the psychological, environmental, and technological challenges of space exploration. By conducting this mission in Wadi Rum, a Martian-like environment, the mission not only showcased Jordan's potential in space research but also fostered collaboration between local and international partners. This section provides an overview of the mission's objectives, timeline, crew composition, and the strategic partnerships that contributed to its success.

2.1 Objectives of PETRA-1

The objectives of the PETRA-1 mission were multifaceted, aiming to enhance Jordan's space research capabilities and add to the global knowledge on analog missions. As the inaugural space analog mission in Jordan, PETRA-1 aimed to show that conducting advanced space simulations in the country is possible, with a focus on interdisciplinary research to tackle the psychological, environmental, and technological hurdles of space exploration.

One of PETRA-1's main goals was to demonstrate the feasibility of upcoming space analog missions in Jordan. The mission successfully carried out in Wadi

Rum—a distinctive Martian-like environment—was intended to demonstrate Jordan's ability to participate in space exploration. PETRA-1 laid the groundwork for developing a space ecosystem in Jordan, showcasing its potential in unique natural resources and capabilities for carrying out analog missions successfully.

PETRA-1 was created for the purpose of investigating and confirming the incorporation of psychological, environmental, and technological studies in space simulation settings. The mission established a novel PET (Psychological, Environmental, Technological) research framework, acknowledging the deep interconnectedness of these areas in the realm of space exploration. Through conducting experiments that covered and intersected between these various fields, PETRA-1 sought to offer valuable knowledge on how potential space travelers may be impacted by the challenges of space missions, how the environment influences various factors, and how emerging technologies can be effectively utilized in support of the mission.

A wider goal of PETRA-1 was to position Jordan as a hub for space research and development. One of JSRI's aims in carrying out this inaugural analog mission was to motivate young scientists, engineers, and innovators in Jordan to pursue opportunities in space exploration. PETRA-1 also sought to foster international cooperation, establishing Jordan as a valuable member of the worldwide space research community.

2.2 Mission Timeline and Funding

The PETRA-1 mission, held from March 19 to March 22, 2024, marked a significant milestone as Jordan's first space analog mission. It was financially supported by a grant from the Jordan 12 program, a program aimed at fostering innovative projects in Jordan. This program, funded by the Innovation Startups and SMEs Fund (ISSF) and implemented by iPARK, provided the resources necessary for the mission's logistics and equipment needs.

The mission unfolded over three distinct phases: preparation, execution, and conclusion.

Phase 1: Preparation

The preparation phase was the longest and most intricate, involving multiple layers of coordination and planning that stretched over several months. The goal was to ensure that every detail was meticulously organized, from research design to the habitat setup in Wadi Rum.

The first step in the preparation phase was defining the mission's scientific objectives and interdisciplinary

research approach. The team developed a mission plan, which included the timeline, research activities, and operational procedures. This phase also involved setting up mission protocols, such as emergency procedures and daily schedules, to mimic the constraints of a Mars mission.

With the mission plan in place, the team began coordinating logistics and establishing partnerships. This included reaching out to organizations for research collaboration and securing equipment. Communication with the Jordan 12 program ensured that the resources would be available on time. Additionally, local partners in Wadi Rum were consulted to assist with site setup and habitat logistics.

Given the harsh desert environment, a thorough risk assessment was carried out to ensure crew safety. This process involved looking into risks related to the weather, preparing backup communication systems, and developing contingency plans for any unforeseen circumstances.

Finally, as the mission date approached, The team coordinated all transportation of materials, equipment, and personnel to the Wadi Rum site, making sure that all necessary resources, such as power, water and food, would be available throughout the mission.

Phase 2: Execution

The execution phase took place during the four days of the mission. It was during this time that the crew, supported by an on-site mission control team, performed a series of tasks designed to simulate the conditions of harsh environments. Each day was broken into scheduled research activities, EVAs, and daily operations within the habitat.

Phase 3: Conclusion

After the mission ended on March 22, 2024, the team worked to finalize the mission and prepare for post-mission reporting. With the research phase completed, the crew carefully packed all equipment and ensured that the habitat was returned to its original state, marking the official closure of the mission site.

Additionally, the team worked to close the financial aspects of the mission by completing grant reporting. A final report was prepared for the Jordan 12 program, summarizing the mission's successes, challenges, and how the funding was utilized. The analysis of data and operational information obtained during the mission is being carried out in order to incorporate lessons learned into future mission planning and streamline operations.

2.3 Crew Composition

The PETRA-1 mission was carried out by an all-female crew of three: Sahba El-Shawa, Lucie Ráčková, and Hope Byrd. The team was already involved in the organization of the mission in various capacities, which was done to ensure that the pilot mission maximized the learning process, enabling the JSRI team to learn firsthand what worked effectively and identify areas for future improvement. Each of the crew members brought unique skills, crucial for the mission's success.

Fig.3. Astro 1, Astro 2, and Astro 3 (left to right)

- **Astro 1: Sahba El-Shawa** served as both the Commander and Mission Engineer. In her capacity as the Mission Director prior to the mission, she handled the main organization during the preparation phase. During the mission, she was in charge of monitoring operations, carrying out technical research, as well as ensuring the safety of the crew and the success of the mission.
- **Astro 2: Lucie Ráčková** was the Sub-commander and Crew Psychologist. She was responsible for conducting cognitive evaluations as well as undertaking all psychological research during the mission. She also was in charge of implementing the physical exercise regimen of the group.
- **Astro 3: Hope Byrd** held the position of Operations Coordinator and Media Lead. She managed daily tasks and implemented data management tools to optimize the operations of the mission. Additionally, she was in charge of all media-related tasks and documentation of the mission for future communications.

This diverse team guaranteed a thorough strategy for the PETRA-1 mission, directly incorporating technical, psychological, and outreach aspects into mission activities.

2.4 Partnerships

PETRA-1's achievements were aided by multiple strategic local and international partnerships:

- **Sun City Camp (Jordan):** Provided the site for the mission and facilities for the living space in Wadi Rum. The camp helped ensure

that the mission crew was isolated at all times. Its existing Martian domes were adjusted to suit the needs of the analog habitat, while guaranteeing that basic necessities like electricity and water were easily accessible.

- **HiGeen (Jordan):** Provided all hygiene and medical supplies to guarantee the well-being and safety of the crew throughout the mission.
- **Dark Side Movement (Czech Republic):** Supplied the exercise regimen for the crew, including training videos, ensuring the team's physical well-being throughout the mission.
- **Plant Melody (Poland):** Provided the framework for an experiment and plant meditation app, promoting mindfulness and connection with the environment. This is further discussed in Section 4..

3. Mission Setup and Operations

The PETRA-1 mission involved careful planning and execution to simulate a Mars-like environment in Wadi Rum, Jordan. The operational structure of the mission was designed to replicate the complexities of a space mission, focusing on habitat setup, crew management, communication protocols, daily schedules, and emergency preparedness. These elements were integrated to create a realistic simulation of the challenges astronauts would face during long-duration missions on Mars, emphasizing both human factors and technological systems. This section outlines the key components of mission setup, operations, and the strategies employed to ensure the success of the PETRA-1 mission.

3.1 Location and Setup

The PETRA-1 mission was conducted in Wadi Rum desert, a UNESCO World Heritage site in southern Jordan, often referred to as the "Valley of the Moon" due to its remarkable resemblance to extraterrestrial terrain. Wadi Rum's red sands and towering rock formations mirror the harsh landscapes of Mars. This desert's vast expanses of rugged, isolated terrain, combined with its geological features, make it an ideal location for simulating space environments and conducting Mars analog research [4].

Wadi Rum presents both benefits and challenges as a Mars analog. On the one hand, its natural topography and the resemblance to Martian geology provide a realistic testing ground for space missions, allowing researchers to study how equipment, habitats, and human factors would perform in extreme conditions. On the other hand, the site is a protected area inhabited by Bedouin communities, meaning that any use of the land must account for both environmental preservation and

cultural sensitivity, in addition to requiring special permits and registrations to operate in the area [4].

While Wadi Rum's remote location presents challenges, such as limited access to essential services and logistical support, the presence of existing tourist infrastructure partially mitigates these obstacles. For the PETRA-1 mission, the team selected an already-existing commercial camp called Sun City, known for pioneering the dome structure in Wadi Rum camps, to serve as the habitat. The Sun City camp offered essential amenities, including access to power and water, reducing the need for complex infrastructure setup. While the dome was initially intended for tourism, it was slightly remodeled to simulate a space habitat, adjusting its interior to accommodate the research objectives of the mission.

Fig. 4. Martian domes in Sun City camp

The rationale behind choosing this site was multifaceted. First, the camp's existing infrastructure allowed the team to focus more on mission operations and less on logistical challenges related to setting up basic resources. Additionally, the use of this pre-existing setup significantly reduced costs, as it eliminated the need for building temporary structures from scratch.

While Wadi Rum provided an exceptional analog to Martian conditions, it also posed several logistical challenges. The desert's remote location required careful coordination to transport equipment and crew. The team also had to anticipate the environmental extremes including potential heavy rain. Despite these challenges, the terrain's partial isolation enhanced the analog experience, offering a testbed for studying human behavior in confinement and solitude, critical factors in future Mars missions. Additionally, the geological features of Wadi Rum allowed for realistic extravehicular activities (EVAs), where crew members could navigate the terrain and simulate planetary exploration. The unique setting helped the mission achieve its goal of mimicking Mars-like operations.

3.2 Mission Control Strategy and Communication

The PETRA-1 mission utilized a mission control strategy that blends both on-site and off-site support. This approach was critical to ensure smooth operations, handle any emergent challenges, and simulate realistic scenarios encountered in space missions.

On-site mission control was established at the Sun City camp, where a dedicated team of two people managed daily operations and handled immediate issues that arose during the mission. This team was responsible for overseeing the implementation of research activities, coordinating EVAs, and ensuring the safety and well-being of the crew. The on-site mission control was equipped with necessary communication tools and monitoring systems to facilitate real-time decision-making and problem-solving.

The off-site control team was set with the objective of offering specialized knowledge and broader perspective on mission operations and assisting with both strategic decisions and unexpected situations if they arose. This coordination would allow the mission to respond rapidly to on-ground challenges while maintaining oversight on broader mission objectives.

Operational procedures were carefully designed to ensure effective coordination between teams. Daily check-ins were conducted to review mission progress, address any issues, and adjust plans as necessary. The team also made use of Notion to manage task lists, track project milestones, and communicate updates in real-time, enabling seamless collaboration between the crew and mission control. This approach ensured that all teams were aligned and could respond swiftly to any changes or challenges that emerged during the mission.

Communication between the crew and mission control primarily relied on a Wi-Fi network that was set up locally and dedicated for the mission, which was generally sufficient for the mission's operational needs. However, given the remote location and the inherent instability of the connection, the team also implemented a radio communication system as a backup. This redundancy was essential for maintaining uninterrupted communication, particularly during critical activities such as EVAs or when Wi-Fi connectivity became unreliable.

A critical aspect of the PETRA-1 mission was the simulation of space-like communication time delays. In a crewed mission to Mars, delays can range from zero to 22 minutes when communicating with Earth [5]. For PETRA-1, a 10-minute communication delay was artificially introduced to mimic the challenges of Mars missions. This delay tested the crew's ability to handle

independent decision-making, as they had to navigate situations with delayed feedback from mission control.

The communication delay was implemented manually, with the mission control team intentionally waiting 10 minutes before responding to any queries or reports from the crew. This approach was designed to mimic the inherent challenges of space communication without relying on complex software systems. While simple in execution, it introduced a realistic layer of difficulty for both the crew and the mission control team. At times, the mission control team would inadvertently respond too quickly, forgetting the imposed delay. This led to moments where the communication delay was not consistent throughout the mission and protocols had to be re-established, which disrupted the flow of the mission due to human error.

3.3 Daily Schedules and Dietary Plans

A structured and well-balanced daily schedule was vital to the success of the PETRA-1 mission. The schedule incorporated a mix of individual and team activities, balancing mission operations, research, physical exercise, and personal time to ensure optimal performance and well-being of the crew.

Fig. 5. Daily exercise and meditation in mission

Each day began at 6:00 AM with the three crew members starting their day with a hygiene routine. Following this, each crew member completed a set of daily psychological and physiological surveys designed to monitor their health and well-being. Breakfast was scheduled after that, offering a shared moment for the crew to gather before the day's activities began. Following that, a daily briefing took place, during which the team discussed the plan for the day, addressing operational priorities and upcoming research tasks.

The daily schedule incorporated research and EVAs, where two crew members performed the EVA and the third stayed back to support operations from inside the habitat. These sessions involved navigating Wadi Rum's Mars-like terrain, hence, simulating the navigation of unfamiliar environments. Additionally, a personal time slot was included everyday. During this hour, the crew was free to take breaks or unwind. It also included physical exercise sessions where each crew member followed an exercise set to ensure they remained in peak physical condition throughout the mission.

Daily meals included breakfast, lunch and dinner. They were planned as an essential part of the mission's dietary strategy. The crew adhered to a specialized meal plan designed to provide the necessary caloric intake, nutrients, and hydration needed to maintain optimal physical and mental performance. The meals were pre-packaged, similar to spaceflight conditions, and included freeze-dried foods only. This diet ensured that the crew could sustain energy levels throughout the day, even during physically and mentally demanding activities like EVAs.

Fig. 6. Preparation of freeze-dried meals

At the end of each day, the crew completed daily reports and surveys to document their activities, observations, and any challenges they faced. These reports were essential for tracking mission progress and provided critical data on both operational outcomes and the psychological and physiological states of the crew. The day concluded with a wind-down routine and lights out at 10:00 PM, ensuring each crew member got ample rest for the next day's schedule.

This balanced schedule of activities, combined with a planned dietary strategy, was essential in maintaining discipline and consistency throughout the mission. It ensured that the crew could operate effectively in the simulated space environment, manage physical and psychological stress, and complete mission objectives.

3.4 Emergency Protocols and Resupply Missions

Safety and contingency planning are paramount in any analog mission, ensuring preparedness for unforeseen circumstances. In the PETRA-1 mission, an emergency protocol was designed to address both medical and operational challenges. The emergency protocol was tailored to simulate a real Mars mission scenario, where immediate external assistance is limited.

Medical contingencies were a top priority, with protocols developed for various potential health emergencies. The crew had access to basic medical supplies sufficient to address common injuries and illnesses. For more severe cases, a pre-designated evacuation plan was established, allowing the transportation of injured personnel to the nearest medical facility in Aqaba, approximately 45 minutes away by car.

These protocols evolved from lessons learned during the planning phase of the PETRA-1 mission, which had been previously documented in the IAC 2023 paper "*First Analog Mission of the Jordan Space Research Initiative: One Small Step for Emerging Space Countries, One Giant Leap for Jordan*" [6]. The earlier study highlighted the need for extensive contingency planning in analog missions, emphasizing the importance of simulating isolation and managing the limitations imposed by external dependencies.

The resupply mission framework in PETRA-1 was designed to mirror the logistical constraints of a Mars mission. Given the remote location of Wadi Rum and the simulation of limited external support, resupply missions were strictly controlled. In a real Mars mission scenario, resupply missions are both costly and rare, hence, the PETRA-1 mission simulated limited external interaction, with a strong emphasis on pre-mission preparation and inventory management. However, provisions and additional supplies, including a water kettle, water, salt, and pepper, were delivered to the crew by the mission control team to ensure their autonomy throughout the mission.

Through careful planning and well-defined protocols, the PETRA-1 mission demonstrated the importance of emergency preparedness and supply chain management in space analog missions. The emergency protocols and resupply missions were designed to provide robust support for the crew, ensuring that they could effectively manage emergencies and maintain operations throughout the mission. These measures were essential for addressing potential challenges and ensuring the mission's success.

4. Research Areas

PETRA-1 integrated psychological, environmental, and technological research to simulate future space mission complexities. The intention behind these research fields was to intersect, highlighting the significance of interdisciplinary methods in tackling the obstacles of space exploration. The mission's emphasis on preparation of humans and technology for extreme environments provided a crucial foundation for future research in analog missions.

4.1 Psychological Research

The psychological research carried out during PETRA-1 aimed to evaluate the impact of isolation and confinement on cognitive function, emotional state, and mental health. The information gathered in this area is essential for comprehending the mental obstacles astronauts could encounter on extended space expeditions.

Cognitive Assessments

These assessments were created to evaluate the team's memory, concentration, and judgment skills in isolated and high-pressure environments. The goal of the findings was to gain understanding of the impact on cognitive abilities during space missions and how they may decline in harsh conditions.

Fig. 7. Completing cognitive assessments

Morning and Evening Questionnaires

Crew mood, well-being, and stress levels were monitored daily through questionnaires. These evaluations yielded significant information on the effects of isolation and confinement on mental health during the mission. The morning and evening check-ins provided insight into mood changes and stress levels at various times. Mission Control was also asked to complete the same questionnaires, to understand how the interactions between crew and MCC were developing.

Environmental Attitudes Survey

This study explored how the crew's view of their surroundings impacted their affinity to the natural environment. The research highlighted the significance of environmental factors on the crew's perception of nature, especially after spending time in enclosed and isolated spaces such as space habitats.

4.2 Environmental Research

Research done during PETRA-1 emphasized the crew's relationship with the desert environment, which closely resembles the difficulties of living in space-like conditions. The experiments were designed to examine the impact of sustainable living systems and environmental factors on mission success and crew well-being.

Plant Meditation Experiment

The study called Plant Melody focused on investigating the mental advantages of plant meditation, in which participants practiced mindfulness by listening to sounds produced by plant vibrations. This study sought to investigate how engaging with plants could enhance mental health in isolated spaces, offering important findings for upcoming missions where astronauts might require psychological assistance by engaging with nature or artificial settings.

Water Reclamation Experiment

The water reclamation experiment looked at using a water recovery method to collect water from the desert. This study added to the field of sustainability, as water is essential for extended space missions. Although the water reclamation protocol does not necessarily replicate the Martian conditions, as it was extracted from the humidity in the desert sand, it may reflect potential in-situ resource utilization experiments including setting up and retrieving them while completing an EVA.

4.3 Technological Research

Having a high level of technological readiness is essential for the success of space missions. During the PETRA-1 mission, various technological tools and preliminary systems were trialed in anticipation of upcoming missions in challenging environments.

Virtual Reality

Virtual reality (VR) was used as a tool during the mission to validate its use as an emerging technology. The VR studies offered a type of environmental meditation, enabling the team to unwind mentally in virtual natural settings, while measuring the effectiveness of the VR simulations on the crew. This was an initial step in using VR during the analog

missions, with potential for further incorporation into the training process and EVA preparations.

Fig. 8. Use of VR in mission

Analog Spacesuits

The crew tested its own analog spacesuits in Wadi Rum's challenging desert environment to simulate EVAs on Mars, including donning and doffing protocols. This research was essential for adding a layer of realism to the EVAs, as well as understanding the impact of restricted mobility and potential limitations astronauts might face during surface exploration on Mars.

Fig. 9. EVA analog spacesuit

The research conducted during PETRA-1 highlighted the significance of using an interdisciplinary approach in exploring space. By combining psychological, environmental, and technological studies, PETRA-1 provided a comprehensive framework for future analog missions which will influence the planning of future

missions to the Moon and Mars. This interdisciplinary research also sets the stage for Jordan to continue contributing to global space exploration efforts in various capacities.

5. Lessons Learned and Recommendations

The PETRA-1 mission provided valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities of conducting space analog missions in a Martian-like environment. By examining both the successes and the areas needing improvement, the mission offered critical lessons for future analog missions in Jordan and beyond. The operational, psychological, and technological findings will help refine future mission designs, with a focus on optimizing crew performance, resource management, and mission simulations. This section details the key lessons learned from PETRA-1 and provides recommendations for enhancing future missions.

5.1 Operational Lessons

The PETRA-1 mission offered valuable insights into the operations of an analog mission. The following lessons were drawn from both the successes and challenges encountered during the mission.

Infrastructure and Isolation

One of the core operational successes of the PETRA-1 mission was the effective utilization of the existing infrastructure in the Sun City camp, which was adapted to function as a Mars habitat. The decision to leverage a pre-built structure significantly reduced the time and resources needed to construct a new habitat, allowing the team to focus on mission-critical objectives. The habitat itself, with its availability of water, power, and basic life-support systems, provided the necessary conditions for the crew to live and work comfortably for the four-day mission.

However, the use of a commercial camp also posed several challenges. For instance, the pre-existing infrastructure was not designed specifically for space analog missions. Although efforts were made to select domes located at the far edge of the camp to allow for some level of isolation, achieving a true sense of seclusion proved challenging. Future missions will need to implement more stringent measures to simulate these constraints of isolation.

Logistics and Coordination

Coordination among the crew was another key operational success. Daily briefings, clear task assignments, and well-structured schedules facilitated the smooth execution of the mission's objectives. The use of Notion to organize tasks, track progress, and ensure real-time updates further streamlined communication and workflow, keeping everyone

aligned. This strategy will be taken forward and expanded upon in future missions.

Communication Delays

Finally, an area for improvement is better implementation and potential automation of communication delays. In PETRA-1, the crew purposely introduced a communication delay to mimic the time lag astronauts would face talking to Earth from Mars. Although this method aims to increase the mission's fidelity, it was manually enforced, which made it difficult to maintain due to human error. Automating the communication delay would enhance realism and decrease operational inconsistencies. By streamlining the delay into the communication method directly, this would guarantee that the delay is consistently implemented, enabling more thorough training and operational readiness.

5.2 Psychological and Social Dynamics

The PETRA-1 mission offered valuable understandings on the psychological and social difficulties that astronauts could encounter on extended space missions. It is crucial for mission success to handle mental health, stress, and team dynamics in isolated environments, and PETRA-1 identified various areas for enhancement and strengthening in upcoming analog and space missions.

Crew Well-being

The mission showed how important it is to uphold daily routines that promote mental well-being, especially in isolated settings. Implementing regular physical activity, organized personal time, and nutritious meals effectively engaged the crew both physically and mentally. However, while these routines provided some stability, PETRA-1 revealed that stress management strategies could be improved, especially for missions that extend over longer periods. Despite the short duration of this pilot mission, the psychological strain of isolation became more apparent as the mission progressed, indicating that future missions should incorporate additional mental health support systems, such as access to remote counseling or more personalized psychological interventions.

Resources and Sustenance

PETRA-1 emphasized the importance of accurate calculations and strategic planning for critical resources, such as food and water. In the simulated Mars-like setting of the mission, the importance of resource management was emphasized, particularly in situations where resupply missions are not possible, such as in long-term planetary exploration. This situation highlighted the importance of having strong backup plans in place to address potential delays or lack of resources. Despite the extra food and water brought in

during habitat ingress, the team used more resources than predicted, utilizing all the extra food supplies and requiring multiple water resupply missions. Future missions should be improved with tighter resource allocation protocols, along with more thorough contingency planning and redundancy.

Team Dynamics and Stress

Effective collaboration and a positive working relationship among crew members were crucial for the mission's success, showcasing the importance of team dynamics. Nevertheless, the mission showed that there is a requirement for additional organized social interaction guidelines to handle the anxiety that may occur due to prolonged isolation and restriction. In a small crew sharing one habitat, where personal space is limited and interactions are constant, it is crucial to create systems that aid in resolving conflicts and providing emotional support. Upcoming missions would benefit from incorporating specific team-building activities or scheduled relaxation time for crew members to relax and bond as a group. Enhancing team cohesion with structured social dynamics can help reduce psychological effects of prolonged isolation, which is important for boosting morale on long missions.

Fig. 10. PETRA-1 crew interaction during mission

5.3 Technological and Environmental Research

The technological and environmental studies carried out during PETRA-1 offered crucial understanding of the tools and systems needed for extended space missions. The task emphasized the need to enhance operational efficiency by refining simulations, improving equipment performance, and integrating new technologies.

Use of Virtual Reality

During PETRA-1, VR was shown to be successful for training and psychological support. However, there is potential for further incorporation of VR into mission activities, especially for mimicking more intricate assignments and urgent situations. Upcoming missions

could leverage broader VR usage which encompasses complete mission practice, scenario-focused instruction, and even remote equipment diagnostics. Through placing crew members in virtual environments, VR can enhance readiness and mitigate the psychological impacts of seclusion and restriction.

EVA Simulations

A major takeaway from PETRA-1 was the significance of mapping EVA sites beforehand to improve the authenticity and scientific worth of the simulations. Despite the fact that Wadi Rum's desert setting was a great substitute for Mars, upcoming missions may be able to gain advantages from further thorough exploration before the mission to pinpoint particular locations that present the most demanding and pertinent conditions for experimentation. Pre-mapping could improve the organization of scientific activities and ensure that EVA simulations closely resemble actual planetary exploration. This would also help avoid EVAs in any areas that may be unsuitable, due to difficulty navigating the terrain or potential of encountering disturbances to the simulation.

Fig. 11. PETRA-1 Crew on EVA in remote location

6. Future Directions

The success of PETRA-1 has laid the groundwork for further advancements in Jordan's space research capabilities. By focusing on scalability and deeper research into space analog missions, JSRI is poised to expand its role in the international space community. This section outlines how PETRA-1 serves as a stepping stone for more ambitious future missions and the impact it has on space research in Jordan.

6.1 Scalability for Future Missions

The PETRA-1 mission serves as a critical proof of concept, demonstrating the feasibility of conducting space analog simulations in Jordan. By leveraging the unique landscape of Wadi Rum and adapting existing infrastructure, PETRA-1 showcased Jordan's potential as a hub for analog space research. This success lays a solid foundation for scaling up future missions, particularly in establishing more complex and sustained simulations that mirror the demands of long-term space exploration.

One of the core visions of JSRI is the development of a permanent habitat that could be used for extended simulations. A long-term research facility, purpose-built for analog missions, would allow for more frequent and comprehensive studies into the psychological, environmental, and technological challenges of space exploration. Such a facility would not only reduce the logistical efforts needed to modify existing infrastructures but also enable more authentic simulations. The ability to perform months-long simulations, rather than short ones like PETRA-1, would bring Jordan's research capabilities on par with other global analog habitats, creating opportunities for deeper research into human factors, mission sustainability, and space operations.

Furthermore, building on the success of PETRA-1, JSRI plans to organize another mission in September 2025. This upcoming mission will focus on refining lessons learned from PETRA-1 and pushing boundaries further by collaborating with other established analog research facilities globally. This will play a pivotal role in scaling up future missions. Sharing best practices and methodologies with teams from global analogs can improve mission design, technology testing, and crew dynamics. These collaborations will strengthen Jordan's position within the international space research community.

Ultimately, the scalability of the PETRA-1 mission goes beyond just its technical and operational achievements. By consistently expanding the scope and complexity of future missions, Jordan can position itself as a leader in space analog research, capable of contributing to global efforts in human space exploration while simultaneously advancing its own space research capabilities.

6.2 Impact on Space Research in Jordan

PETRA-1 has significantly enhanced Jordan's presence in the global space research sector, establishing the country as a key player in analog missions and space exploration, despite its limited resources. The mission has demonstrated Jordan's ability to contribute meaningfully to international space research,

highlighting its unique environmental and technical assets as essential to advancing the field of analog research.

Additionally, PETRA-1 has opened new doors for JSRI to partner with space agencies, research institutions, and organizations both globally and locally. These collaborations will drive further innovation in space research and development, creating opportunities for Jordan to strengthen its role in the space community.

JSRI continues to be the main driving force pushing forward space research in Jordan. Through missions like PETRA-1, JSRI is fostering international collaborations while nurturing the next generation of Jordanian scientists and engineers passionate about space exploration. The successful coordination and execution of PETRA-1 have demonstrated that Jordan can be a valuable contributor to global space research, particularly in conducting analog missions that simulate Martian habitat conditions.

Through its extensive efforts, JSRI is establishing Jordan as a key player in space research, and creating a framework for other emerging space countries to follow in its path.

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